

Polyethylene Degradation by Pseudomonas Putida

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Abstract

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The most common polymer in plastics is polyethylene (PE), which is made from ethylene monomers ($CH_2=CH_2$). In natural form it is not biodegradable. Low density polyethylene is a vital cause of environmental pollution. Low density polythene (LDPE) is the most widely used packaging material primarily because of its excellent mechanical properties, barrier properties against water, light weight, low cost and high energy effectiveness. Present study investigates an eco-friendly; efficient and cost-effective approach for plastic waste management by the screening of novel microbial consortia which are capable of degrading plastic polymers. *Pseudomonas putida*, could grow optimally at 37 °C in pH 9.0 and showed 25–30% of plastic weight reduction over 60 days. Protein, Carbon source estimation and weight loss measurements in the positive control (*pseudomonas putida* with plastic LDPE) was found to be 11% to 34% with a degradation capacity when compared to Treated (*pseudomonas putida* -UV induced, with plastic LDPE) for 60 days, C=O, strength or elongation analysed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), structural analysis in GCMS were found out two compounds.

Keywords: Polyethylene degradation, mutation induced (UV), *Pseudomonas putida*, protein and carbon source, weight loss measurements, FTIR, GCMS.

Introduction

Plastics are an integral part of our day to day life and are being used in packaging, building materials and for many other purposes (Gnanavel et al. 2012). The speed of technological change is increasing remarkably such that life in 2030 will be unrecognizable compared to that of today; plastics will play a substantial role in this change (Andrady and Neal 2009). Despite the advantages that plastics have over many other polymers, the fact remains that it is nondegradable and not eliminated from the environment efficiently (Zubris and Richards 2005). Due to their stable nature, they tend to accumulate in the environment causing severe pollution (Hemashenpagam et al. 2013; Tserki et al. 2006; Kim et al. 2007; Ray et al. 2007). Improper recycling and waste management systems in developing countries are majorly responsible for plastic pollution (Jayasiri et al. 2013). Many studies showed that several efforts have been made to eradicate plastic wastes in the different parts of India (Kathiresan 2003; Hemashenpagam

et al. 2013; Jayasiri et al. 2013); however, the success rate is not satisfactory. Bangalore considered as the one of the cosmopolitan cities in India, with nearly eight million people and generates about 4000 tonnes of garbage every day, major portions of them are plastic wastes. Due to the unscientific disposal of plastics and other.

Waste, the pollution has risen to unprecedented level in urban and rural areas of Bangalore, India. Recent report suggested that the plastic waste management has become a major environmental concern along with industrial and vehicular pollution (Hemashenpagam et al. 2013).

The industries which manufacture plastic bags and other materials are bound to release waste products containing both solid and liquid forms of plastics, and these wastes are directly dumped in soil and aquatic ecosystems. The long-chain polymers released from such xenobiotic compounds are persisted in the environment for a very long time and accumulated in living tissues and undergoes biomagnifications (Tokiwa et al. 2009; John et al. 2012). Hence, there is a high priority to address these issues and identify novel eco-friendly strategies to detoxify or degrade the plastic materials from the ecosystem.

Enzymatic degradation is one of the main approaches that exist for plastic waste management by microorganisms. These microbial enzymes are successful in increasing the rate of biodegradation of plastic polymers effectively without any detrimental impact to the ecosystem (Bhardwaj et al. 2012; Wu et al. 2000; Shah et al. 2008). The microbial degradation is proven to be eco-friendly because of its non-toxic end products such as CO₂, H₂O and CH₄ (Shah et al. 2008).

Materials and Methods

Microorganism collection

The bacteria *Pseudomonas putida* (MTCC NO: 2467) used in this study were procured from Microbial Type Culture Collection and Gene Bank (MTCC), Chandigarh. Cultures were maintained on LB agar plate. Plastic is polyethylene (PE) as commercial plastic carry bags of LDPE were collected and cut into small strips and subjected for Chemical - alkali treatment.

Chemical - alkali treated polyethylene

Polyethylene bags were cut into small strips & transferred to fresh solution containing 18ml tween, 10ml bleach, and 225ml of distilled water & stir it to 30-60mins. Bleach consists of 5gms of sodium chloride, 5gms of sodium hydroxide & 10 ml of glacial acetic acid. Strips were transferred to beaker with distilled water & stir it 2 one hour.

Total biomass

About 1ml of the culture was transferred into 1.5ml micro centrifuge tube & pelleted down at 12000rpm at 4°C for 25 min. The pellet was dried overnight at 50°C & dry weight of the resulting biomass was calculated

Analysis of the LDPE Film Biodegradation

Weight Reduction Measurement

The weight after duration three intervals of incubation was compared to the mass before incubation. For comparison the mass of film in the control was also measured. The percent weight reduction was calculated with the formula:

% weight reduction: ---

$$\frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times 100 \text{ ---(1)}$$

W₁

Where, W1 is the weight of polyethylene film before incubation and W2 is the weight of polyethylene film after 15 days, 30 days and 60 days of incubation.

1. Induction of mutation by UV
2. Biomass weight
3. Total sugar in the Culture Supernatant

The total sugars were analyzed by anthrone method. Glucose was used as the standard & the absorbance was measured at 495nm (Hansen J, Møller IB 1975).

The total protein concentration in the supernatant was determined by the method reported by Bradford. Bovine serum albumin solutions were used as standards and absorbance was measured with a spectrophotometer at 595nm.

Spectroscopic Analysis

The changes in the polymer bonds due to biodegradation were determined using FTIR-AT spectrophotometer. The plastic films exposed to all the four strains of bacteria were analyzed at regular intervals.

GC-MS Analysis

A wide variety of both volatile and semi volatile compounds were eluted by gas chromatography. GC-MS was performed for samples incubated with *Pseudomonas putida*.

Results

Fig: 1 bacterial plates showing *Pseudomonas putida*- Positive control and two different incubation periods: 30 days and 60 days.

This study observed a 0.02 to 0.01 reduction in the weight of plastic strips (Fig: 1, table - 1) and a 11– 34 % reduction in weight of plastic films (table-4) over an incubation period of 60 days. From these results, it is clear that the rates of degradation for plastic strips by microorganisms are slightly faster than that of the plastic pellets. This is probably due to difference in the surface area of plastic strips and pellets. In plastic strip, more numbers of bacteria can colonize because of wide surface areas.

Biomass Estimation

Table 1 -- LDPE films exposed to mutation induced *Pseudomonas putida* Biomass Estimation with 2 different incubation periods: 30 days and 60 days

Days	Control	Positive control	UV 30 days	UV 60days
30 days	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.02
60 days	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.01

Protein Estimation

Table 2 ---LDPE Films Exposed to Mutation Induced Pseudomonas Putida Protein Estimation with 2 Different Incubation Periods: 30 days and 60 days

60 days	Control	Positive control	UV 30 days	UV 60 days
Concentrated 2mg/ml BSA	1.73	1.55	0.91	0.61
Diluted 1mg/ml BSA	1.25	1.18	0.63	0.56

Sugar Estimation

Table 3 ---LDPE Films Exposed to Mutation Induced Pseudomonas Putida Sugar Estimation with 2 Different Incubation Periods: 30 days and 60 days

60 days	Control	Positive control	UV 30 days	UV 60 days
Concentrated 1M Glucose	1.96	1.89	1.12	1.00
Diluted 0.5m Glucose	1.49	1.45	0.77	1.54

Table 4 Weight Loss of Low Density Polyethylene Film

Sample	Initial weight of the film	Mass of film after 60 days incubation (mg)	Percentage reduction in mass
Control (P.putida)	1.000	1.000	0.00
Positive Control (P.putida + LDPE)	1.000	0.890	11%
Test -01 P. putida (UV mutated :30 days) + LDPE	1.000	0.780	22%
Test -02 P. putida (UV mutated :60 days) + LDPE	1.000	0.660	34%

The dry weight of LDPE films were measured at different time points during the course of Incubation, the result represents the average of triplicate experimental data's.

FTIR

In the present study FTIR results in Positive Control: Pseudomonas Putida with LDPE showed that 1417.49 cm⁻¹ to 1454.29 cm⁻¹ O-H, 1641.53 cm⁻¹ C=C, and 2988.57 cm⁻¹ C-H, peaks were stretched in the treated group of Pseudomonas Putida (UV induced) with LDPE (60 days), i.e. 1420.55 cm⁻¹ to 1457.35 cm⁻¹ O-H, 1641.35 cm⁻¹ C=C, and and 2981.50 cm⁻¹ C-H, respectively

GC–MS Analysis

A wide variety of both volatile and semi volatile compounds were eluted by gas chromatography. GC–MS was performed for samples incubated with *Pseudomonasputida*. The degradation products after exposure to *Pseudomonas putida* include long chain fatty acids, esters, hydrocarbons, oxygenated chemical compounds predominantly containing aldehydes, ketones, esters and ether groups, unsaturated fatty acids and certain unknown compounds and also alkanes (such as Octadecane, and Hexacosane), fatty acids (such as Hexadecanoic acid and Octanoic acid), ester group of alcohols.

Presence of 4, 6-Octadiyn-3-one, 2-methyl which is a ketone in addition to 4,4-Dimethyl-2-pentene which is an alkene in the culture supernatant through GC-MS detection can be attributed to the process of biodegradation of the polymer where ketones are part of the intermediary products

Discussion

Hence, present study suggests that the plastic materials with more surface area and planar geometry may degrade in faster rate. Similarly, other probable parameter responsible for the degradation efficiency of microorganisms is the position of the functional groups in the hydrocarbon chain. There are reports which revealed that the degradation of plastics by bacteria and fungi are very slow processes and the degradation efficiency is mainly depending on the position of functional groups and other side chains in the aromatic ring. If the side chain is in meta-position, microbial degradation may take place in faster rate than the ortho and para positions.

These findings support the previous work on biodegradation of LDPE under natural environmental conditions although in vitro studies have not been fully investigated using individual bacterial strains (Kyaw BM, et al 2012).

Past research has isolated *Pseudomonas putida* from sludge in industrial waste and determined that it used *o*-chloronitrobenzene (*o*-CNB) as its only carbon, nitrogen, and energy source. Most importantly, the highest degradation of *o*-CNB (85%) by *P. putida* was found to be at 32°C and a pH of 8.0. Although *o*-chloronitrobenzene is not plastic, this research gives a general idea of ideal growing conditions for *P. putida*, and shows that it is capable of using one source as its only carbon, nitrogen, and energy source (Brown BS, et al 1974).

Recent studies reported that there was 20% reduction in the weight of polythene films over an incubation period of 120 days (Kyaw et al. 2012). Another study suggested that there was 25–45% reduction in the weight of plastic strips incorporated as carbon source in liquid media inoculated with the samples collected from waste disposal sites, drainage sites and soil from sewage sludge (Nanda et al. 2010).

There are many studies reported that molecular docking and computational simulations have crucial role to understand the biodegradation mechanism of various xenobiotic compounds by microbial enzymes. These approaches pave significant insight towards detoxification mechanism of various lead molecules and thereby understand the mechanism of stable binding of hydrocarbon derivatives to the active site of the enzymes (Rengachari et al. 2013; Cao et al. 2011; Bosma et al. 2002).

Use of weight reduction as a measure of the extent of polyethylene biodegradation has been widely accepted and used by many authors (Ojha N, et al 2017, Sheik S, et al 2015 & Deepika S, Jaya MR. 2015). These outcomes are in agreement with (Pramilla R, et al 2015) who reported the ability of microorganisms to degrade virgin polyethylene.

C-H, peaks were stretched in the treated group of *Pseudomonas Putida* (UV induced) with LDPE (60 days), i.e. 1420.55 cm⁻¹ to 1457.35 cm⁻¹ O-H, 1641.35 cm⁻¹ C=C, and 2981.50 cm⁻¹ C-H, respectively are indicative of formation of aldehydes and ketones which are intermediate products of biodegradation of polyethylene.

The current study has drawn conclusion based on experimental analysis performed for a limited period of time. The study can be further extended for along period with many replicates which may give more consistent results. However, it is assured that the present study paves foundations to carry out such kinds of long term analysis.

Future Prospective

Recent report suggested that the microbial consortia formulated from highly diverse environmental microflora which share similar composite phylum showed high degradation of lignocellulolytic and other types of polymers (Wongwilaiwalin et al. 2013).

As biodegradation by microorganisms is a slow process, this study need to be extended further for long periods. In the current study, the consortia were formulated using two isolates which showed better degradation than known strains; hence, other microorganisms responsible for plastic degradation are also needed to be screened, characterized and formulated.

These organisms can be used as effective microbial consortia for better degradation of various types of long-chain polymers. Present data provide crucial insights for many future concerns and perspectives.

The *Pseudomonas putida* GPO1 (commonly known as *Pseudomonas oleovorans* GPO1) alkBFGHJKL and alkST gene clusters, which encode proteins involved in the conversion of n-alkanes to fatty acids, are located end to end on the OCT plasmid, separated by 9<7 kb of DNA. This DNA segment encodes, amongst others, a methyl-accepting transducer protein (AlkN) that may be involved in chemotaxis to alkanes. In *P. putida* P1, the alkBFGHJKL and alkST gene clusters are flanked by almost identical copies of the insertion sequence IS_{Ppu4}, constituting a class 1 transposon.

Other insertion sequences flank and interrupt the alk genes in both strains. Apart from the coding regions of the GPO1 and P1 alk genes (80±92 % sequence identity), only the alkB and alkS promoter regions are conserved. Competition experiments suggest that highly conserved inverted repeats in the alkB and alkS promoter regions bind AlkS (Jan B. van Beilen, et al 2001).

Plastic Recycling Symbol	Plastic Name	Where to Find This Plastic in Your Home	This Plastic is Valued For
 LDPE	Low-density Polyethylene	food bags, squeezable bottles, cling films, disposable cups	flexibility ease of processing ease of sealing barrier to moisture

Conclusion

The current study aimed to devise approach of long-chain hydrocarbon degradation by microorganisms such as bacteria, *Pseudomonas putida* by induced mutations. Further screening and characterization of the best plastic-degrading isolates can be utilized. To achieve higher rate of degradation, the growth parameters for the isolated bacteria were optimized at which 34 % reduction in weight of plastic was observed in a span of 60 days, it could be ideal to subject LDPE or polyethylene degradation for a long term may be 240 days.

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